

DIGITAL DISCOURSE TO THE ENGLISH-LANGUAGE FICTION

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Abstract: The development of modern literature, particularly English-language fiction, cannot be imagined without the influence of digitalization on these processes, as more and more access to English-language fiction is provided through digital media. The aim of this article is to determine the influence of digital media on the development of English-language fiction on the example of support of publishing houses Bloomsbury Publishing and Sourcebooks. The proposed approach to determine the impact of digital media on the development of English-language fiction reveals the importance of the impact of the support of publishing companies, using Bloomsbury Publishing and Sourcebooks as examples, on the development of English-language fiction through digital media.

Keywords: Digital Media, Digitalization, English-Language Fiction, Modern Literature, Publishing House.

1 Introduction

The modern development of English-language fiction, as well as foreign fiction, takes place in the context of digital discourse under the influence of digitalization. The role of digitalization in the development of English-language fiction is manifested in the fact that it makes the features of English-language fiction better known; as access to works of English-language fiction becomes more open not only to English speakers, but also to others. Thus, it is possible to read English-language fiction not only for English speakers but also for others, using various on-line translators. Access to English-language fiction is much easier now than it was before the digital revolution. Users can read English-language literary fiction both in paper (book) form and in online using various ICTs. The digitalization of libraries plays an important role in the development of English-language fiction, through which a list of literary works available in a particular library can be obtained. Besides digitalization of usual libraries, the place in development of the English-speaking fiction is occupied by online libraries, which every Internet user has an access to. Publishers (publishing houses) play an equally important role in the process of development of English-language fiction, because thanks to them existing literary works are republished and new ones are issued, in particular works from English-language fiction.

2 Literature review

Mangen (2016) notes that the current stage of literary development is not without the influence of digitalization. The number of users who read literary works online or with the help of various ICTs is increasing. Such trends, according to the scholar, act as determinants in the development of literature. Skains (2019) also notes that an important milestone in the development of fiction under the impact of digitalization is the use of modern technology to write literary works of fiction. Al-Sharqi et al. (2020), looking at the impact of modern technology on the development of English-language fiction, note that the genre of short stories, that is, short stories based on a new English-language dialect, is developing at a fairly rapid pace in English-language fiction and simultaneously due to the impact of digitalization. This genre, according to scholars, acts as a new stage in the development of English-language fiction under the influence of digitalization. Parkin A. (2019) explores the impact of digital technology on the development of fiction, drawing on his own experience as a writer. The researcher and writer simultaneously notes that the digital revolution, which began in

the late twentieth century, has positively affected the development of fiction. One of the positive effects of digitalization on the development of fiction, according to Parkin, has been the shift from typed literary texts to digitized literary texts. Straub (2021) notes that under the influence of digitalization, works of English-language fiction are not only being created faster by their creators, but are also spreading at a faster rate than when the first phase of the digital revolution was not yet underway.

Tonra (2020) examines the development of Ireland's literary heritage in the context of the digitalization of works of fiction. The scholar notes that digitalization has a multifaceted impact because on the one hand, it enriches and on the other hand, it degrades the value of the tangible work of English-language fiction. Rippl et al. (2021), exploring the particularities of the digitalization of books, including works of fiction, pay particular attention to the particularities of digital editing and cataloging of manuscripts from the Middle Ages. Bode (2019) also holds that the development of literature depends on the impact of digitalization on these processes. Pianzola et al. (2020) highlight the importance of the influence of the Wattpad platform on the development of literature, as this platform allows literary works to be read digitally, including online. Egnal (2013), looking at the characteristics of the development of novels as a genre form of English-language fiction in the United States, notes that they can be accessed through the Ngram database. This online accessibility indicates that English-language fiction in the United States is evolving under the influence of modern technology. Gardner et al. (2017) examine the impact of digitalization on the development of English-language fiction through the digitalization of the ballad of Mary Hamilton, composed back in the sixteenth century by an anonymous author in Scotland. Sanford (2019) explores the characteristics of the development of fiction in England and notes that the literary works of early eighteenth-century England are already digitized and are in digital archives. Apurva (2016) explores the specifics of the digitalization of English-language works in India and notes that the development of English-language fiction in this country has been more rapid due to digitalization than, for example, the development of foreign-language fiction in this country due to those means of digitalization. Biyana (2017) also shares the position of the positive impact of digitalization on the development of English-language fiction and emphasizes the importance of the use of ICT in the development of English-language fiction in India.

Riddell et al. (2020) point out that the digitalization of libraries is important in the development of English-language fiction. The more English-language fiction is available online, the greater and simultaneously positive impact such processes have on the development of English-language fiction. Okeke et al. (2015) note that the digitalization of university libraries, including those institutions of higher education whose profile focuses on the development of fiction, is important for the development of fiction. Underwood et al. (2020) also examine the development of English-language fiction in the context of library digitalization. The scholars examine the characteristics of the development of English-language fiction between 1700 and 2009 using the example of the HathiTrust digital library, which, according to the scholars' research, has 210,266 works of English-language fiction. Sharma (2021) notes that digitizing libraries is necessary to preserve rare works. Therefore, following such a thought, the scholar argues that all libraries should start the process of digitization, as it will not only provide an opportunity in the long run to preserve works of literature, in particular rare among them, but also increase the number of users of such works, in turn, directly affecting the development of literature.

Focusing on the general aspects of the development of English-language fiction, we note that the issues of development of English-language fiction under the influence of digitalization on these processes remain insufficiently disclosed.

The purpose of this article is to determine the impact of digital media on the development of English-language fiction, using the example of the support of the publishing houses Bloomsbury Publishing and Sourcebooks. In order to achieve the aim of the research, we will conduct a correlation and regression analysis of the variables that allow us to show the impact of digital media on the development of English-language fiction.

3 Materials and research methods

The research uses: 1) methods of theoretical analysis, induction, deduction and abstraction - to present theoretical and practical aspects of the development of English-language fiction under the impact of digitalization on these processes; 2) methods of measurement, observation, comparison, description, hypothesis, generalization - to determine the impact of digital media on the development of English-language fiction. While determining the impact of digital media on the development of English-language fiction will be carried out on the example of Bloomsbury Publishing (Bloomsbury Publishing plc., 2021a), which is one of the largest publishing houses in the UK and specializes in publishing English-language fiction, and Sourcebooks (Sourcebooks, Inc., 2021), which is one of the largest publishing houses in the United States and also specializes in publishing English-language fiction. These two publishing houses are chosen from the list of publishing companies represented by Publishersglobal (2021).

The following indicators form an information base of the research:

- Bloomsbury Publishing's revenue from the sale of English-language fiction book products through digital media (including E-books, Audio, BDR and other digital revenues) (Bloomsbury Publishing plc, 2021b, 2020, 2019, 2018, 2017);
- Bloomsbury Publishing's total revenue from the sale of English-language fiction book products (Bloomsbury Publishing plc, 2021b, 2020, 2019, 2018, 2017);
- Sourcebook's income from the sale of English-language fiction book products through digital media (Sourcebooks, 2021);
- Total income of Sourcebooks from the sale of English-language fiction book products (Sourcebooks, 2021).

4 Results

We can acknowledge that the increase in the volume of the realization of book products of English-language fiction through

digital media directly affects the development of English-language fiction as one of the literary trends. Turning our attention to the theme of the research, the independent change in the correlation and regression analysis will be the change in income from the sale of book products of English literature through digital media, and by a relative change - the change in the total income from the sale of book products of English-language fiction. With the help of these indicators we will show how digital media influence the development of English-language fiction, based on the hypothesis that that the increase in the volume of sales of book products from English-language fiction through digital media, as a means of current digitalization, has a positive impact on the development of English-language fiction.

Because Bloomsbury Publishing sells English language art books not only in Great Britain, but also in the United States, Australia and India, We will use the example of this publishing company to show how English-language arts literature in Great Britain, the United States, Australia, and India is evolving due to the impact of digitalization.

Information about the income from the sale of English-language fiction book products through digital media and the total income from the sale of English-language fiction book products by Bloomsbury Publishing is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: The revenue of Bloomsbury Publishing from the sale of English-language fiction book products through digital media and the total revenue from the sale of English-language fiction book products, thousands of sterling pounds

Types of income/Countries where book products are sold	Period				
	2016-2017	2017-2018	2018-2019	2019-2020	2020-2021
Income from the sale of English-literature book products through the digital media					
Great Britain	4,194	4,925	5,112	5,625	8,867
United States of America	2,502	2,441	2,792	2,895	5,481
Australia	0,780	0,791	0,824	0,893	1,247
India	0,197	0,240	0,316	0,388	0,339
Total income from the sale of English-language book products					
Great Britain	46,664	59,957	56,112	55,535	65,934
United States of America	27,832	29,721	30,637	28,579	40,727
Australia	8,684	9,623	9,035	8,821	9,263
India	2,194	2,920	3,470	3,835	2,436

Source: calculated and systematized by the authors based on Bloomsbury Publishing plc, 2021b, 2020, 2019, 2018, 2017

In view of the absence of data on the income from the sale of English-language fiction books through digital media and the total income from the sale of English-language fiction books by the publishing house Sourcebooks, we sent a list to the electronic mail to this company to provide information about the income from the sale of book products of English-language fiction through digital media and the total income from the sale of books of English-language fiction. Having obtained the necessary information from Sourcebooks and systematized it, we will present the income from the sale of books of English language fiction through digital media and the total income from the sale of books of English-language fiction by the publishing house Sourcebooks in Table 2.

Table 2: Sourcebook's income from the sale of book products of English-language fiction through digital media and the total income from the sale of book products of English-language fiction, \$ million. U.S.

Types of income	Years				
	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Income from the sale of English-language fiction book products through the digital media	65,895	66,261	64,129	67,562	66,986
Total income from the sale of book products of English-language fiction	158,478	147,526	145,257	151,587	153,298

Source: calculated and systematized by the authors based on information received from the Sourcebooks, 2021

According to the results of the correlation and regression analysis, we obtained the appropriate values of the correlation coefficient (Table 3, Table 4). To make a qualitative assessment of the link between the change in total revenues from the sale of book products of English-language fiction and the change in the size of the total revenues from the sale of English-language fiction. The relationship between the total incomes from the sale of book products of English language fiction through digital media is determined by the Cheddock's scale.

The analysis of Table 3 suggests that there is a direct relationship between the variable of total revenue from English-language fiction book sales.

Table 3: Results of the correlation analysis according to Bloomsbury Publishing

Countries	Linkage and correlation	The correlation coefficient
Great Britain	Direct link, high correlation	0,824491
United States of America	Direct link, high correlation	0,973527
Australia	Direct link, low correlation	0,195833
India	Direct link, middle correlation	0,692069

Source: calculated by the authors

In terms of the level of relationship density, then a high level of relationship density between the variables under consideration is present for countries such as the United Kingdom and the United States. This indicates that publishing house Bloomsbury Publishing's total revenue from English-language fiction book sales is highly correlated with revenue from English-language fiction book sales through digital media in the United Kingdom and the United States. Such results, in turn, indicate that in the United Kingdom and the United States (as derived from the publishing house Bloomsbury Publishing analysis), digital media have a significant impact on the development of English-language fiction in those countries. Given the significant relationship between the variables, the publishing house Bloomsbury Publishing by increasing book sales through digital media, increases total book revenue. The results indicate that the more consumers use this company's book products through digital media, the greater will be the impact of digital media on the development of English-language fiction.

In other countries, for example, the level of correlation density between the variable of total income from English-language fiction book sales and the variable of income from English-language fiction book sales via digital media is weak in Australia, where the publishing house Bloomsbury Publishing sells book products, and medium in India. These results suggest that the impact of digital media on the development of English-language fiction supported by Bloomsbury Publishing in India is not significant, but slightly higher than in Australia.

Focusing on the results of a correlation analysis based on data from Sourcebooks, which sells book products in the United States, then it is found that there is a direct relationship between the variable total income from English-language fiction book sales and the variable income from English-language fiction book sales through digital media, but the level of density of this relationship is moderate. This indicates that the impact of digital media on the development of English-language fiction in the United States supported by the publishing house Sourcebooks Publishing is not significant (Table 4).

Table 4: Results of the correlation analysis according to Sourcebooks

Linkage and correlation	The correlation coefficient
Direct link, middle correlation	0,446201

Source: calculated by the authors

The analysis of the coefficient of determinacy obtained by Bloomsbury Publishing shows, that the variation in total revenues from the sale of English-language fiction book products is due to the variation in revenues from the sale of English language fiction book products through digital media in Great Britain by 67, 97%, in the United States by 94.77%, in Australia by 3.83%, and in India by 47.89%. These results indicate that the digital media through which English-language art books are sold to consumers in the United States is having a significant impact on the growth of English-language art

literature. Here we note the significant impact of digital media on the development of English language fiction in the United States, supported by Bloomsbury Publishing. Taking into account the coefficient of determinacy according to the regression analysis of Great Britain and India, we should note that the impact of digital media on the development of English-language fiction according to the obtained results is not high or moderate.

Regarding the coefficient of determination based on the results of the regression analysis of Australia, our assumptions about the significant influence of digital media on the development of English-language fiction (based on data from Bloomsbury Publishing) for this country are not confirmed. Although it is acknowledged that, the official language of Australia is English, unlike in India, where the official language is Hindi and digital media with the support of Bloomsbury Publishing are developing English-language arts literature.

The coefficient of determination calculated by the Sourcebooks publishing company indicates that that the variation in total income from the sale of English-language fiction book products is due to the variation in income from the sale of English-language fiction book products through digital media in the United States by 19.90%. This result indicates that the overall income from the sale of English-language fiction book products is not strictly dependent on the income from the sale of English-language fiction book products through digital media. Therefore, according to this data, we can say that digital media does not significantly influence the development of English-language fiction through the support of Sourcebooks Publishing Company in the United States.

5 Discussion

In the course of revealing the purpose of the study, the particular relevance of the problem of the influence of digital media on the development of English-language fiction is revealed. In particular, Mangen (2016), Skains (2019) and Al-Sharqi et al. (2020) noted that digitalization, using modern ICTs, constitutes a particular influence on the development of literature, including the development of English-language fiction. We quite agree with the position of these scientists, because, as practice shows, the availability of literary works, in particular works from English-language fiction online, as well as because of the use of ICT, gives to many people, who are interested, an opportunity to read these works at a convenient time and in a convenient place.

Digital discourse as a strand of English-language fiction provides:

- The transition from typed literary texts to digitized literary texts (Parkin A., 2019);
- Not only the rapid creation of literary works by their creators, but also the rapid dissemination, since, thanks to modern technology, literary works are available online faster in libraries than in book form (Straub, 2021; Pianzola et al., 2020; Egnal, 2013);
- Digitalization of libraries and the creation of online libraries (Riddell et al., 2020; Okeke et al., 2015; Underwood et al., 2020; Sharma, 2021).

While we should certainly agree with the conclusions in the research studies mentioned above, let us note that publishing companies (publishers) also play a special role in the development of English-language fiction. Because of the use of modern ICTs, in particular digital media created in the context of digitalization, English-language fiction essays are not only quickly issued, but also sold to end users. Given the importance of the influence of publishing companies on the development of English-language fiction in the context of digitalization, we chose to study digital discourse as a direction of development of English-language fiction, based on the definition of the impact of digital media on the development of English-language fiction. Thus, to determine the impact of digital media on the development of English-language fiction, we conducted a correlation and regression analysis between the dependent variable of total book revenue from English-language fiction and

the independent variable of book revenue from English-language fiction through digital media.

The results of our correlation and regression analysis showed that in the United States of America, supported by Bloomsbury Publishing, digital media significantly influences the development of English-language fiction in this country. For example, in the United States, the variation in total book revenue from English-language fiction is driven by a 94.77% variation in book revenue from English-language fiction through digital media. The impact of digital media on the development of English-language fiction supported by Bloomsbury Publishing in the United Kingdom is found to be somewhat lower than in the United States, as the variation in total English-language fiction book revenue is driven by the variation in English-language fiction book revenue through digital media in this country of 67.97%. The influence of digital media on the development of English-language fiction supported by Bloomsbury Publishing in India is determined to be not significant, but slightly higher than in Australia. The impact of digital media on the development of English-language fiction in the United States supported by Sourcebooks Publishing is found to be insignificant, as the variation in total English-language fiction book revenue is only 19.90% due to the variation in English-language fiction book revenue through digital media in this country.

6 Conclusion

We found that digital media have a positive impact on the development of English-language fiction. To determine the impact of digital media on the development of English-language fiction, a correlation-regression analysis based on data from one of the largest UK publishing companies, which specializes in publishing English-language fiction, i.e. Bloomsbury Publishing, and is one of the largest publishing companies in the United States, also specializes in publishing English-language fiction, i.e. Sourcebooks. The results of the correlation and regression analysis allow us to note the particular importance of the influence of digital media on the development of English-language fiction in the United States with the support of Bloomsbury Publishing. The practical significance of the information obtained from the results of the correlation and regression analysis is that the proposed approach to determining the influence of digital media on the development of English-language fiction reveals the importance of the influence of the support of publishing companies, using the example of Bloomsbury Publishing and Sourcebooks, on the development of English-language fiction through digital media. The approach to determine the impact of digital media on the development of English-language fiction by correlation and regression analysis is universal, as it can be used to determine the impact of digital media on the development of English-language fiction with the support of libraries, as they also act as actors providing not only the development of English-language fiction, but also other literary trends. In the perspective of further research, it is planned to determine the impact of digital media on the development of English-language fiction supported by libraries.

Literature:

1. Al-Sharqi, L., & Saeed Abbasi, I.: *The Influence of Technology on English Language and Literature*. English Language Teaching, 13(7). 2020 <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v13n7p1>
2. Apurva, A.: *Why Digitization of Regional Literature is Essential*. Entrepreneur. 2016 <https://www.entrepreneur.com/article/286872>
3. Biyana, S.: *Role of ICT in english literature and teaching aptitude*. International Journal in Management & Social Science, 5(6), 2017. pp. 1-6.
4. Bode, K.: *A world of fiction: Digital collections and the future of literary history*. University of Michigan Press, 261. 2019 <https://library.oapen.org/bitstream/handle/20.500.12657/23996/1006138.pdf?se>

5. Bloomsbury Publishing plc. *Results for the year ended 28 February 2017*. https://www.bloomsbury-ir.co.uk/docs/librariesprovider16/archives/annual_reports/prelim-presentation2017.pdf
6. Bloomsbury Publishing plc. *Results for the year ended 28 February 2018*. https://www.bloomsbury-ir.co.uk/docs/librariesprovider16/archives/annual_reports/prelim-presentation2018.pdf
7. Bloomsbury Publishing plc. *Results for the year ended 28 February 2019*. https://www.bloomsbury-ir.co.uk/docs/librariesprovider16/archives/annual_reports/prelim-presentation2019.pdf
8. Bloomsbury Publishing plc. *Results for the year ended 29 february 2020*. https://www.bloomsbury-ir.co.uk/docs/librariesprovider16/archives/annual_reports/prelim-presentation2020.pdf
9. Bloomsbury Publishing plc. 2021a. <https://www.publishersglobal.com/directory/publisher-profile/1885>
10. Bloomsbury Publishing plc. 2021b. *Results for the year ended 28 February 2021*. https://www.bloomsbury-ir.co.uk/docs/librariesprovider16/archives/i_presentations/preliminary-results-presentation-fy21.pdf
11. Egnal, M.: *Evolution of the novel in the United States: The statistical evidence*. Social Science History, 37(2), 2013. pp. 231-254.
12. Gardner, A.-C., Hundt, M., & Kindlimann, M.: *Digitization of the Mary Hamilton papers*. Journal Article, refereed, original work, 41(1), 2017. pp. 3-30. <https://doi.org/10.1515/icame-2017-0004>
13. Mangen, A.: *The Digitization of Literary Reading: Contributions from Empirical Research*. Orbis Litterarum, 71(3), 2016. pp. 240-262. <https://doi.org/10.1111/oli.12095>
14. Okeke, I. E., Udem, O. K., & Onwurah, B.: *Digitization of Library Resources in University Libraries: A Practical Approach, Challenges and Prospects*. Madonna University Journal of Research in Library and Information Science, 3(2), 2015. pp. 36-47.
15. Parkin, A.: *Digitization and Literature: The Approach of a Poet-Critic to Digital Influences on Poetry and Fiction with Special Reference to My Own Experience as a Writer*. In: Tso A. (eds) Digital Humanities and New Ways of Teaching. Digital Culture and Humanities (Challenges and Developments in a Globalized Asia), 1, 2019. pp. 55-69. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-1277-9_4
16. Pianzola, F., Rebora, S., & Lauer, G.: *Wattpad as a resource for literary studies. Quantitative and qualitative examples of the importance of digital social reading and readers' comments in the margins*. PloS one, 15(1). 2020 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0226708>
17. Sanford, S.: *Review of Novel Ventures: Fiction and Print Culture in England, 1690-1730 by Leah Orr*. ABO, 9(2). 2019 <https://doi.org/10.5038/2157-7129.9.2.1205>
18. Sharma, S.: *Preservation and digitization in modern and heritage libraries of Jammu Province: an analytical study*. Annals of Library and Information Studies (ALIS), 68(2), 2021. pp. 119-126.
19. Skains, R. L.: *Teaching digital fiction: integrating experimental writing and current technologies*. *Palgrave Commun*, 5(13). 2019 <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-019-0223-z>
20. Sourcebooks. 2021 <https://www.sourcebooks.com/>
21. Sourcebooks: *Publishing company profile*. 2021 <https://www.publishersglobal.com/directory/publisher-profile/6642>
22. Straub, J.: *Literary Reviewing and the Velocity of Book Histories in Times of Digitization*. Anglia, 139(1), 2021. pp. 224-241. <https://doi.org/10.1515/ang-2021-0011>
23. Tonra, J.: *Digital Bibliography and the Irish Book Trades. Studies in Eighteenth-Century Culture*, 49(1), 2020. pp. 337-341. <https://doi.org/10.1353/sec.2020.0029>

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